

An automatic approach for left atrium regional segmentation in atrial fibrillation patients by including anatomical variations in pulmonary veins and appendage

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Background: The study of the left atrium (LA) is increasingly attracting the interest of the scientific community. Unlike the left ventricle, a standardized approach for regional segmentation of the LA is not available, and this topic is still a matter of investigation, in particular for arrhythmias characterization. This study sought to define an automatic technique to divide LA into well defined standard regions by considering anatomical variations in pulmonary veins (PVs).

Methods and Results: 3D patient-specific anatomical models were derived from CT through an active contour segmentation algorithm. The first detected region was the left atrial appendage (LAA) by applying a thresholding approach based on shape diameter function values. Then the algorithm automatically calculated the barycenter of each PV and excluded the extra PVs by considering their area and position. Furthermore, these points were used to detect the roof and the posterior wall. The line connecting the weighted barycenter of the PVs and the center of the mitral valve (MV) was defined as the long axis of the LA. The annulus of the MV was divided into four equal parts allowing to extract four points. The boundaries of the anterior, inferior, lateral, septal regions were detected considering the position of these four points on the MV and of the centers of the PVs. To validate the results of the proposed approach, an expert electrophysiologist graded the result of segmented regions as: unacceptable, poor, fair, and good. We considered 10 LA models from atrial fibrillation (AF) patients having a varied number of PVs, size, and location and different LAA shapes; the algorithm ran on all cases and successfully divided the LA into seven regions. The grading of the expert was fair and good in 3 and 7 patients, respectively.

Conclusions: This proposed approach was effective in dividing the LA into seven standard regions irrespective of the variation in number, size, and location of pulmonary veins. It represents a first step towards the quantification of regional LA function and contraction. Further testing is required to confirm these results by including a greater number of atrial fibrillation patients.

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